

SELECTION OF METHODS FOR STATISTICAL PROCESSING OF RESULTS OF RADIOMICS ANALYSIS OF CT IMAGES OF JAW TUMORS

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Abstract. *Purpose of the study: to determine the diagnostic value of using radiomics in the differentiation of benign and malignant jaw lesions on MSCT images. A retrospective radiological analysis of CT images was performed in 65 patients with histologically and clinically verified jaw tumors (28 benign and 37 malignant tumors). LIFEx 7.10 software (C. Nioche, F. Orhac, etc.) was used for textural analysis. Results: Using the Kruskal-Wallis test, 1 out of 39 textural parameters - DISCRETIZED_AUC_CSH - showed statistically significant differences between benign and malignant jaw tumors ($p < 0.05$). From the selected textural feature, a predictive model was constructed using logistic regression. $PredDis = 1 / (1 + \exp(-1.02914 - 0.0044970 * DISCRETIZED_AUC_CSH))$. The regression values calculated from the model by logit transformation were normalized in the range from 0 to 1 and used as textural heterogeneity indices. Conclusion: Textural analysis of CT images allows for non-invasive prediction of the benign or malignant nature of upper and lower jaw tumors. The textural heterogeneity index, calculated from the logistic textural model, has the highest predictive accuracy. Textural analysis transforms standard computed tomography into a multiparametric study, complementing the qualitative assessment of anatomical details of the visualized formation with a quantitative functional indicator characterizing intra-tumor spatial heterogeneity.*

Keywords: *spatial heterogeneity, textural analysis, computed tomography, jaw tumors.*

Introduction

Maxillofacial neoplasms account for 20-25% of other tumor diseases [2]. Among jaw tumors, benign neoplasms occur in the vast majority (96-99%) of cases. The significance of radiological examination in detecting this pathology is due to the fact that benign tumors often do not have a characteristic clinical picture and are distinguished by an asymptomatic course in the early stages of growth, and sometimes with a prolonged course of the process. In some cases, jaw neoplasms that have reached significant sizes become a random X-ray finding when patients apply to dental clinics for dental treatment. In the structure of morbidity, mandibular malignant tumors account for 0.2 - 1.4% of human malignant tumors [1, 2]. They belong to the category of extremely severe diseases characterized by a prolonged asymptomatic course and significant diagnostic difficulties. Malignant tumors quickly spread to neighboring structures and, by the time they are recognized, typically infiltrate several areas. For this reason, in later stages, it is sometimes difficult or impossible to establish the initial location of the tumor. On the other hand, despite being widespread locally, such tumors rarely metastasize to distant organs.

The final diagnosis is made based on the histological examination of biopsies of the affected area. Histological evaluation is considered more sensitive than cultivation. Visualization using radiological diagnostic methods is very important and useful for assessing the degree of the

disease. Radiation diagnostic methods, particularly multispiral computed tomography (MSCT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), occupy a significant place in the diagnosis of maxillofacial tumors. MSCT is a selective method for visual assessment of bone structures, the presence of calcification, and can also reveal fluid levels and bone destruction, but its capabilities are limited in the differential diagnosis of tumors from soft tissues and reactive changes in the jaws. MRI better differentiates the tumor, reactive effusion, and mucosal edema, allowing for more accurate determination of tumor size and its extent. So far, the issues of radiation diagnostics of maxillofacial formations remain poorly studied.

Lesions on MSCT and MRI images are usually visually assessed based on the anatomical details of the lesion, such as localization, shape, size, contour clarity, invasion of adjacent structures, etc. However, the information contained in the images about the internal characteristics of the tumor, developing at an indistinguishable microscopic level, remains inaccessible when visually assessing the images. In particular, this refers to the spatial heterogeneity of malignant tumors arising from the chaotic nature of angiogenesis and the heterogeneity of cell proliferation, oxygenation, and metabolism. At the same time, spatial heterogeneity can be assessed using MSCT and MRI images using the radiometric analysis method. Textural analysis allows for the determination of quantitative indicators of spatial heterogeneity of tumors at an indistinguishable microscopic level. With the effective use of radiomics, it is possible to non-invasively characterize the nature of education to individualize treatment and solve the problem of heterogeneity, meeting the standards of accurate and evidence-based medicine. The heterogeneity of a tumor, as established, determines its biological behavior; the more heterogeneous the tumor, the more aggressive and resistant it is to treatment [1,2,3].

This report presents the results of studies on the use of CTTA for the differentiation of jaw tumors.

Material and methods. Textural analysis of routine CT images was performed retrospectively in 118 patients with jaw tumors, including 67 with malignant tumors and 51 with benign tumors. Morphological verification, based on pathohistological studies of tissue samples obtained during endoscopic or open biopsy, was present in all 67 patients with malignant tumors and in 51 patients with benign tumors of jaw bone tumors. In the remaining 17 patients, the benign tumor diagnosis was based on comprehensive examination data, including endoscopy, computed tomography, and was confirmed by typical clinical manifestations and disease progression. MSCT in all patients was performed on a "Somatom Emotion 6" computed tomograph (Siemens, Germany) in a spiral mode with a tomographic cut thickness of 1.5 mm, pitch - 1.0, at a voltage of the X-ray tube of 100-120 kV, with a current strength of 100-200 mA. Computed tomography was performed without contrast enhancement; an alternative method for obtaining functional information using textural analysis of routine non-contrast CT images was studied.

Postprocessing included two stages: in the first stage, a qualitative visual analysis of CT images was conducted, in the second stage, images were evaluated based on the quantitative textural parameters of intra-tumor spatial heterogeneity. At the next stage, CTLT was performed, which consisted of several sequential actions: 1. outlining the area of interest (ROI); 2. Programmatic extraction of intratumoral spatial heterogeneity textural indicators; 3. Selection of significant textural indicators; 4. regression analysis of selected indicators with the construction of a logistic textural model; 5. ROC - analysis of the logistic regression indicator with the determination of threshold levels-orientations for stratification of head and neck tumors. To extract textural indicators, the LIFEx program, version 6.30 [4], was used, which allows extracting various

textural indicators using first, second, and higher-order statistical methods. First-order textural indicators were derived from the histogram of discretized values of image voxels, regardless of their spatial distribution. Second-order textural indicators give signs of spatial arrangement of voxel intensities in a certain order and are derived from the matrix of gray level coincidences GLCM (Gray_level co-occurrence matrix). High-order textural indicators were derived from the GLRLM grey level length matrix (Gray_level run length matrix), the NGLDM neighborhood grey level difference matrix (Neighborhood Gray_level difference matrix), and the GLZLM grey level zone length matrix (Gray_level zone length matrix). All image textural analysis actions, except for manual ROI outlining, were performed by computer using mathematical statistics methods and programs.

Results. In each individual case, from the outlined ROI on CT images, using a textural analysis program, 1 out of 39 textural parameters - DISCRETIZED_AUC_CSH - showed statistically significant differences between benign and malignant jaw tumors ($p < 0.05$). To find a single indicator that integrally reflects intracancerous heterogeneity, a regression analysis of significant textural indicators was conducted with the construction of logistic models, in which the independent variables were in accordance with the given limitation of association from one textural indicator selected during machine processing of data. From the selected textural feature, a predictive model was constructed using logistic regression: $\text{PredDis} = 1 / (1 + \exp(-1,02914 - 0,0044970 * \text{DISCRETIZED_AUC_CSH}))$.

The regression value calculated from the model by logit transformation was normalized in the range from 0 to 1 and used as textural probability indices.

Table 1

Indicators of ROC analysis of textural indices of the probability of logistic textural models of discrimination of jaw tumors according to CTTA data (n=118).

No	ROC analysis indicators of derivative models	Model for the differentiation of malignant tumors from benign ones n=118.
1.	Area under ROC-AUC curve (M±m)	0,892 P<0.0001
2.	95% confidence interval	0,807 - 0,948
3.	Sensitivity %	71,4
4.	Specificity %	95,6
5.	Accuracy %	89,2
6.	Optimal threshold level	0,69
7.	Independent predictors of the model*	$\text{PredDis} = 1 / (1 + \exp (-1,02914 - 0,0044970 * \text{DISCRETIZED_AUC_CSH}))$

The data presented in the table indicate a significant predictive value of logistic texture models. The discriminatory capabilities of the created ROC logistics models were clearly demonstrated by the textural probability index curves, which are derivatives of the models' regression equations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. ROC-curves of the indices of the logistic models of jaw tumors according to CTTA data for the differentiation of malignant tumors from benign ones;

One of the practically important features of ROC analysis is the ability to find the threshold value point of the predictor, which serves as a benchmark for classifying the studied states. The optimal threshold for classifying the visualized formation on CT as benign or malignant jaw tumors in our study was the value of the textural probability index of the model, equal to 0.69 (Table 1 and Figure 1). The values of the probability texture index below the specified threshold were characteristic of benign tumors, while in malignant tumors, its high values prevailed, exceeding the threshold value.

Examples of CT studies with textural analysis from among the patients we examined with jaw tumors can serve as confirmation. One textural indicator, which entered into the constructed logistics models as an association of independent predictors, individually had a lower predictive ability than the probability textural index obtained from the model (Table 2). From the data presented in the table, it can be seen that the indicators of the ROC-texture predictor curves, on the basis of which the logistic regression model was built, were lower than those of the ROC-texture probability index curve.

The traditional approach to differentiating tumors based on visualized classical malignancy criteria, such as irregular shape, unclear (uncertainty) contours, and invasion of adjacent structures, allowed us to correctly predict the malignant nature in 76.5%, slightly inferior to the corresponding indicator according to CTTA data, where it was 81.5%. However, it should be taken into account that with CTT, the possible influence of a subjective factor related to the professional experience and qualification of the radiologist describing the image is excluded.

Figure 2. Patient T., 24 years old. Clinical diagnosis: ameloblastoma. Histological examination: ameloblastoma A- on MSCT in the axial section in the projection of the lower jaw on the right reveals an oval-shaped formation with clear smooth contours, homogeneous structure, density +35+43 unitsH, approximate sizes of 2.8x1.6x1.4cm. B- histogram of distribution of pixels of gray levels in unitsH. The histogram shows symmetry and smoothness of the edges of TIG=0.506.

Figure 3. Patient Z., 56 years old. Histology - Squamous cell carcinoma G-3. A- on MSCT in the axial section in the projection of the lower jaw on the right, an irregularly shaped volumetric formation with unclear irregular contours, homogeneous structure, density +45+54 unitsH, approximate dimensions of 3.85x3.0x2.17cm is determined. B- histogram of distribution of pixels of gray levels in unitsH. The histogram of the formation texture was distinguished by pronounced asymmetry and unevenness of the edges TIG=0.702.

Discussion. Determining the benign or malignant nature of tumors localized in the jaw area before surgery is often difficult. Due to the anatomical complexity of the tumor localization region, puncture biopsy is not always possible and not always effective, and moreover, it is an invasive procedure. Tomographic imaging methods, particularly computed tomography, provide significant assistance in the differential diagnosis of the jaw. However, the classical signs of malignancy or benignity visualized on CT images can often overlap, making it difficult to predict the probabilistic nature of the formation. In these cases, CTTA of tumor images can be helpful, allowing for a

quantitative assessment of intracancerous heterogeneity, which increases significantly in malignant tumors.

Our studies have shown the possibility of using a quantitative index of textural heterogeneity to differentiate benign and malignant jaw tumors, confirming the results of recent studies on the use of textural analysis for this purpose [5,6]. However, the indications for textural analysis can be significantly expanded. These include the stratification of highly differentiated cancer from low-differentiated cancer, predicting the molecular-genetic status of the tumor, predicting the tumor's response to treatment, and improving control over its outcomes, among others. [7,8,9,10,11].

Studies in this area are still few in number, performed using various CTTA methodological approaches at the stages of extracting textural indicators, their subsequent statistical processing to select the most significant features, and determine the criteria for classifying certain characteristics of tumors according to selected textural features. Some researchers limit themselves to using individual histogram indicators or grey level occurrence matrix for these purposes, while others prefer to construct logistic textural models using grey level and higher-order matrix indicators [12,13]. The same can be said about the applied mathematical programs for extracting textural indicators from images, their selection to reduce the space of textural features, etc.

The lack of unified approaches to textural analysis is the main factor hindering the implementation of this technology for processing medical images. It is important to combine efforts to standardize textural analysis methodology and expand research on the reproducibility of results.

The progressive growth of publications on the issue under consideration encourages that textural analysis of medical images will become one of the most in-demand technologies for analyzing medical images.

Conclusion

CT image textural analysis is a new area of medical research that allows for non-invasive virtual biopsy of human tissues and predicts the benign or malignant nature, as well as other characteristics of the visualized formation in the jaw region. The probability index, calculated from the logistic textural model, has the greatest predictive accuracy. CTTA transforms standard computed tomography into a multiparametric study, supplementing the qualitative assessment of anatomical details of the visualized formation with quantitative functional indicators characterizing intra-tumor spatial heterogeneity, which allows for improving the results of diagnostics, tumor differentiation, as well as determining treatment tactics and predicting outcomes.

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